

DEVELOPMENT OF A NOVEL STATIC SEAL FLUTTER RIG

Fabian Hualca
Imperial College
London, UK

Christoph Schwingshackl
Imperial College
London, UK

Richard Setchfield
Rolls Royce Plc
Derby, UK

Jon Gallego
Rolls Royce
Derby, UK

Detlef Korte
MTU Aero Engines AG
Munich, Germany

Roque Corral
Universidad
Politecnica de Madrid
Madrid, Spain

Michelle Greco
Universidad
Politecnica de Madrid
Madrid, Spain

Oscar Bermejo
ITP Aero Engines
Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a novel seal flutter test facility- designed, assembled, and commissioned by the Structural Dynamics Group, at Imperial College London. The test facility has been developed under the European Union Horizon-2020 ARIAS Project, in partnership with work package partners, Rolls-Royce Plc, MTU Aeroengines AG, ITP Aeroengines and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM).

The aim of this development is to build a unique test rig, to be able to study the dependence of seal flutter, for a wide range of flow conditions, seal geometries and seal tip clearances. The design of the test facility was driven by a set of predetermined requirements, which were agreed to by all the work package partners. The final design of the flutter rig was based on a combination of existing, partially validated codes from different work package partners, previous 'know-how' and experience gained from present aeroelastic and structural dynamic test rigs, in the UK and Europe. A unique, modular test rig has been developed, that allows for the investigation of a wide range of test conditions. In addition, a series of different analyses have been conducted, to ensure the structural integrity of the rig and its operating performance.

Section 1 introduces the problem and discusses past and current research on seal flutter. Section 2 provides a detailed discussion of the rig design, analysis and assembly, followed by a description of the operating procedure and initial commissioning tests. Section 3 discusses the results and section 4 provides a conclusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

In gas turbines, labyrinth seals are used to control the volume of leakage flow that passes from the high-pressure side of the seal to the low-pressure side, between the rotating and stationary components of the engine. Leakage flow causes unfavourable losses to the cycle efficiency of the engine, and hence it is important to attenuate or control the leakage flow. This problem affects a vast range of rotating machinery, including gas turbines, turbo compressors, turbo pumps and steam turbines [1].

The rotating element of the seal is generally flexible and prone to large vibration amplitudes, which can lead to high cycle fatigue (HCF) and consequent seal cracking. The most common aerodynamically induced vibrations of seals are due to flutter, which is a self-excited phenomenon produced by the interaction between the aerodynamic forces, the elastic response of the structure and the inertial forces. It is a positive feedback mechanism, where the structural response increases the aeroelastic force, and can potentially lead to an uncontrollable amplitude increase [2]. It is important to be able to understand, predict and control flutter, to prevent unexpected seal failure.

Typically, the rotating parts of a labyrinth seal in an engine are equipped with a series of fins (see Figure-1), which throttles (controls) the flow, making the kinetic energy near the proximity of the fin tips get diffused, in the inter-fin cavities. Compared with simple annular slit seals, the introduction of fins can significantly reduce the leakage flow by up to by 40%, therefore the geometry and fin tip clearance play a vital role in controlling leakage flow across the seal [3].

During an aeroelastic stability study, conducted by Abbott [4] in 1980, it was found that the ratio of the seal natural frequency to the acoustic frequency in the inter-fin cavities

strongly affected seal instabilities. In addition, theoretical results showed that, apart from the ratio of natural frequency to acoustic frequency, the seal support side also played a vital role in the stability of the seal. Abbot's results were verified by actual labyrinth seal tests.

Further to Abbot's study, Ehrich [5] used an analytical model to show that the seal clearance influenced the stability of the seal significantly. Ehrich compared both stable and unstable seal designs. Both studies were later confirmed by Lewis *et al.* [6] in their analytical and experimental test campaign, with turbofan engine geometries. After conducting an inspection of cracked seals, the authors concluded that most cracked seals were fitted with very tight tip clearances, prior to testing. Subsequently, a real engine test demonstrated that a seal can be stabilised by increasing the clearance gap at the first fin of the seal.

More recently, Coral *et al.* [6,7] have introduced an analytic model, to predict the behaviour of a labyrinth seal. Further highlighting the impact that seal clearance, pressure ratio, natural frequencies, and seal geometries can have on the seal stability.

Most of the work on labyrinth seal flutter, has focused on numerical prediction of the stability, but in 1997, a report was published on a research programme (ROSTADYN) that focused primarily on the negative effects that results from decreasing the seal tip clearance of labyrinth seals [9]. The experimental study aimed to investigate, theoretically and experimentally, the physical interaction between rotors and stators, for the turbomachinery industry. During this research programme, the authors concluded that their inhouse predictive software was accurately validated by the experimental data obtained from the test rigs and industrial gas turbine seal experience. Furthermore, the results also showed the importance of major controlling parameters that influenced the stability of labyrinth seals, e.g., acoustic frequency relative to structural frequency and support side of the seal. The evidence generally supported the analysis of Abbott [3]. More recently, a test rig has been developed by Kawasaki Heavy Industries [10], which allows the testing of a seal under rotating conditions with pressure ratios up to 3. The rig consists of two opposing seals to balance the seal load, and has a basic set of instrumentation installed, to identify the resulting seal vibrations. Successful seal flutter was induced during the tests, providing high quality validation data for the numerical models.

FIGURE-1: ENGINE REPRESENTATIVE LABYRINTH SEAL.

The available experimental data does allow for the validation of some of the prediction techniques, but unfortunately, it does not provide the physical insight of what is going on inside the seal cavities during a flutter event. Furthermore, the accessible parameter space is rather limited, due to the design of the rigs. To overcome these issues, a new test rig has been developed under the Horizon 2020 ARIAS project, with a specific aim, to allow the widest possible parameter space to be explored, whilst providing very detailed flow and structural measurements during the experiments. In this paper the development, design, installation, and initial commissioning of the seal flutter rig will be discussed.

2 DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND ASSEMBLY

The main objective of the newly designed labyrinth seal flutter rig, at Imperial College London, is to validate high fidelity data of seal flutter events, for a variety of seal designs and a wide range of operating parameters. Table-1 summarises the main test requirements for the test rig.

TABLE-1: MAIN OPERATING CONDITIONS OF THE SEAL FLUTTER RIG.

RIG SPECIFICATIONS	
Max pressure (bar)	6
ΔP (bar)	< 5
Fin tip-clearance (mm)	0.2, 0.7, 1.2
Seal diameter (mm)	~ 350
Number of fins	< 4
Flow rate (kg/s)	< 1.2
Frequency rage (kHz)	< 10

2.1 Design approach

The design approach taken was based on a combination of existing and partially validated codes, from the different work package partners [7], existing aeroelastic and structural dynamic test facilities, and many internal discussions, to ensure the facility would deliver the required performance. The software used to design the seal flutter rig was SolidWorks 2021.

The main features of the test facility can be summarised as follows:

Modular assembly— allows the cavity sections and the test specimens to be easily and rapidly replaced, modified, and instrumented for greatest test flexibility.

Symmetric design— a symmetric design allows a high degree of flexibility, with respect to the seal-flow configuration and the seal support arrangement.

Conical test section— the inside wall of the test section is conical, which allows various seal-tip gap clearances to be tested in a single test campaign (see Figure-1).

Advanced instrumentation— a wide range of instrumentation is available, to measure steady and unsteady flow, steady deflections, and dynamic behaviour of the test specimens.

Diverse test specimens— the experimental test facility will allow the study of seal behaviour, for a variety of seal geometries, number of fins and seal supports.

Tuneable cavities— radial and axial modular inserts allow control of the acoustic resonance frequencies inside the rig’s plenum cavities.

Non-rotating design— this feature eliminates the inherent complexity and cost of a rotary rig, instrumentation, and operation under rotating conditions. The behavioural differences between, rotating and static test pieces, are overcome through careful design of the rig, test articles and the use of piezo-electric actuators.

FIGURE-2: BASIC SKETCH OF THE SEAL FLUTTER RIG: FLOW DIRECTION 1 → 2

Figure-2 highlights the basic functionality of the ARIAS seal flutter rig. The seal is supported by a long slender shaft that fits concentrically inside the test section; the shaft is supported at the two extremes by the end cylinders. On either side of the test section there are tuneable acoustic cavities, that allow the acoustic resonances to develop and the flow to settle. Air is injected and ejected from the rig, through the inlet sections, while the large axial load of the seal, caused by the pressurisation, is counteracted by the end cylinders. During a test, one side of the rig will be pressurised, whilst the other side will be kept at a lower pressure, to induce flow across the rig and initiate seal instability. Due to the symmetry of the rig, the flow direction can be configured without opening the rig or making modifications to the setup.

FIGURE-3: KEY FEATURES OF THE SEAL FLUTTER RIG.

A more detailed layout of the rig’s main components can be observed in Figure-3. Different tapered seal designs (8) can be attached to the long, slender shaft (13) via a keyless bushing (9). The shaft is supported at both ends with micro-metre stages (1), that allow precise and ultra-fine radial positioning of the seal within the conical test section (7), to ensure an even fin gap all around. The axial position of the shaft, which determines the fin gap clearance in the test section, is controlled by two fine threaded bolts (12). The bolts also help transmit the large axial forces generated by the seal, when the rig is fully pressurised. The test section (7) has been machined out of a single block of steel, to extremely high tolerances, to ensure an even fin gap all around. It has a smooth and conical interior shape that allows various fin gaps, ranging from 1.2 to 0.2mm, via an axial realignment of the seal. It should be noted that, this realignment feature can be accessed externally and does not require modifications or disassembly of the rig. The test section has many access ports that hold a variety of instrumentation, for the inter fin cavities of the seal. On either side of the test section the rig design is symmetric, with cavities (6) connected to it. The cavities ensure an even and well-controlled flow distribution to the test section, which allows the capability of studying acoustic phenomena. Inserts (14) can be attached to the inside walls of the cavities and can be used to change their volume, to tune/mistune the acoustic response. Due to the way the seal is supported on the shaft, no additional features obstruct the flow in the cavities. The cavities themselves are also heavily instrumented to study the flow conditions at the entrance and exit of the test section. Behind the cavities (6) are the inlet cylinders (5), which condition the flow and allows the air to enter or exit (3 and 11) the rig, depending on the flow direction. To ensure a uniform and non-swirling flow into the cavities, a series of honeycomb panels (4) are placed inside the inlet sections, as well as a duct cylinder (10) which further stabilises and guides the flow into the cavities. The two end cylinders (2) of the rig, contain the shaft support system and were designed to handle the large axial loads during operation. Except for the test section, all casings are split horizontally, so that the interior of the rig can be easily accessed when a new seal is introduced, or modifications to its configuration are required. Due to the symmetric configuration of the inlet and outlet, air can be supplied to either end of the test rig, allowing a reversal of the flow across the seal, without the need to reconfigure the test setup. Air is supplied to the test rig by three industrial-scale compressors, where each compressor outputs clean/dry air at a temperature of 15°C.

2.2 Numerical analysis of rig

Two types of metals were chosen for the FEA simulations of the rig, steel 17-4-PH-1150 with a yield-strength of 720MPa, and steel S355J2-G3 with a yield-strength of 330MPa. Steel 17-4-PH-1150 was chosen for the shaft and seal, to handle the large axial loads during operation and to achieve as little deformation possible. The rest of the rig was simulated using steel S355J2-G3. The software used for the simulations was SolidWorks 2021.

FIGURE-4: HOOP-STRESS CONTOURS IN N/M², TEST SECTION WITH HOLE FEATURES.

An independent simulation was run just for the test section (Figure-4) since it is the most important part of the rig. The model included all its complex features (a total of 146 instrumentation ports). The material chosen for this analysis was S355J2-G3 with a yield-strength of 330MPa. The results revealed a hoop-stress of 2.94MPa, providing confidence that no stress related failures would be observed. Although not shown here, an independent simulation was also run for a simplified test section (without complex features), to understand the effect the complex features have on the structural integrity. The simplified test section achieved a hoop-stress of 2.7MPa. Therefore, the test section with complex features achieved only ~5% higher hoop-stress values than the test section without. Providing confidence on the simplification made and demonstrating that the various hole features has not impacted the structural integrity of the test section.

FIGURE-5: DEFORMATION CONTOURS OF THE ASSEMBLED CYLINDERS.

An FEA model comprising of the rig assembly was simulated, to study the overall deflections of the entire rig. The model was simplified by removing the inlet and outlet pipes, as well as the instrumentation ports and threaded holes to reduce complexity in the mesh and save computation cost. Results for the general

deformation distribution of the rig assembly can be seen in Figure-5. A maximum pressure of 6bar was simulated, which produced a maximum deformation below 4μm, in the test section. This value meets a critical design requirement for the test section, ensuring a well-controlled tip gap clearance.

FIGURE-6: HOOP-STRESS CONTOURS OF THE RIG.

Results for the hoop-stress distribution of the rig assembly can be seen in Figure-6. A maximum pressure of 6bar was simulated, which produced a maximum hoop-stress of 11.6 MPa on the downstream shaft-support cylinder, which is significantly below the yield strength, and hence the test rig can be considered safe against plastic deformations, due to the internal pressure.

The seal under full load (pressurisation) will generate up to 50kN of axial load, which needed to be counteracted by the end sections. To ensure the integrity of the axial support cylinders, a concentrated pressure load was applied, representing the force introduced by the loaded shaft. The computed results in Figure-7 showed a maximum stress of 76 MPa, which led to a safety factor against failure of more than 4. The load resulted in a 14 μm deflection, which was considered acceptable since its impact on the seal fin gap size was negligible.

FIGURE-7: STRESS CONTOURS DUE TO AXIAL LOADING IN N/M².

In addition to the static FEA simulations on the main cylinders, the dynamic behaviour of the shaft was analysed, with and without representative seal masses at its centre. Some basic

buckling analysis led to the selection of a solid shaft of 45mm diameter, to ensure the axial loads of the fully loaded seal could be transmitted safely.

The seal specimens were designed and simulated (FEA) by our work package partners, Rolls Royce Plc and MTU Aero Engines. These designs were based on predictions from full 3D-CFD and the Corral-Vega method [7], with the aim to deliberately produce test specimens that are unstable under certain operating conditions. A large amount of effort was placed on the design of the seal, its support and positioning inside the rig, to ensure that it would become unstable during testing, but also so that it could cope safely with the static and dynamic stresses it will experience during testing.

FIGURE-8: COMPARISON OF UNSTEADINESS BETWEEN NO-TILT (A) AND TILTED (B) INLET PIPE. THE INLET PIPE (B) HAS A TILT ANGLE OF 11.25°.

The inlet geometry designed was based on the outcome of an unsteady CFD analysis, which was carried out with the inhouse code AU3D, to improve the flow characteristics at the inlet. The first design (Figure-8a) showed a high velocity jet that collided with the shaft and generated high unsteadiness in the flow. To smoothen the flow, the inlet pipe was shifted by a small angle, to miss the central seal support shaft (see Figure-8b). This improved the unsteadiness of the flow but gave rise to high magnitudes of swirl, therefore, a second pipe was added to the lower section of the inlet, to reduce the swirl (see final design in Figure-3). CFD simulations were also conducted to design and optimise the flow from the inlet section into the cavity to ensure an even and steady flow at the test section inlet (see Figure-9). This resulted in the addition of an inlet duct cylinder (see (10) in Figure-3), which ensured an even flow field inside the cavity.

FIGURE-9: CFD ANALYSIS FOR OPTIMIZED FLOW INTO CAVITY.

Based on the FEA and CFD results, and after several design iterations, a final rig design was obtained, that could be manufactured. The complete CAD design of the test facility can be seen in Figure-10.

FIGURE-10: COMPLETE 3D-CAD DESIGN OF THE SEAL FLUTTER TEST FACILITY, ENCLOSED BY A SOUND-BOOTH.

Figure-10 shows a detailed illustration of the rig’s pipework (air supply), flow monitoring and control instrumentation (A, E, F, H, J, K), control boxes (B, D, G, I) and the overall rig assembly. Although not shown in Figure-10, a mass-flow meter is located above the ceiling of the sound-booth. Air is supplied by three Ingersoll rotatory-screw compressors, capable of providing a combined mass-flow of 1.2kg/s, at a pressure of 7Bar. However, for the purpose of the experiments, the primary pressure regulator (K) features a maximum mass-flow of only 0.5kg/s, a maximum pressure of 6bar and a minimum pressure of 3Bar. Airflow can travel from left-to-right or right-to-left, depending on the type of test to be conducted. The flow direction can be set by manually opening and closing valves (V₂, V₃, V₄ and V₅) accordingly. Once the flow direction is set, actuator-valves (F, H and J) and pressure controller (A) can be configured. Once the manual valves, actuator-valves and pressure controller have been set, the rig can be pressurised. In case of an emergency, a PLC (programmable logic controller) can execute a safe shutdown procedure of the rig, mainly to protect the seal, in case of high amplitude events. The PLC and other electronic devices are powered by the mains power supply; however, in the event of power loss, a backup UPS (universal power supply) was connected, to mitigate any power issues with the emergency shutdown. In addition, an emergency manual valve (V₆) has been installed outside the sound-booth, to act as a second backup to stop airflow going inside the rig. All the data and control of the rig is handled by an advanced control system (B and D). The data acquisition systems (B and D) facilitate the capture of measurements through many data channels, simultaneously and at high sampling frequencies, to ensure high-quality data.

2.3 Rig instrumentation

The test rig is heavily instrumented to ensure that each flutter event can be monitored and recorded with a high degree of accuracy. Both, flow and structural dynamic data are available, to obtain a better physical understanding of the events, and provide high quality validation data. Currently, the test rig has more than 200 access locations, that allow measurements of air temperature, steady and unsteady pressures across the rig and in the inter-fin cavities, as well as the seal location and dynamic response.

The test section is, by far, the most heavily instrumented section. Sensors can be mounted for different seals, with 1 to 3 inter-fin cavities, and up to six circumferential locations. There is a complete set of seal measurement locations, in three axial locations, for the three seal fin gap clearances (1.2, 0.7 and 0.2mm). Due to the many possible configurations, all instrumentation is mounted on holders which can easily be moved around the test section, to accommodate for the different test requirements. In its current state, six unsteady pressure probes (Kulite XCL-100) have been installed circumferentially, to resolve up to six Nodal Diameters (ND6). A similar number of static pressure probes will be used initially, to understand the flow conditions inside the inter-fin cavities (limited by the current 12 channel Scanivalve DSA3127 scanner). The channels can be easily swapped, so depending on the test requirements, different locations on the rig can be scanned. The seal position inside the test section, and the relative motion of the seal due to static loading as well as vibration, are measured via three confocal sensors (Keyence CL-P015), with a resolution of 0.003 micrometres. The sensors are distributed circumferentially, at relative angles of 120°, and measure radial displacement of the inter-fin cavity hub. In addition, a set of nine USB cameras are used to align the seal axially and provide some basic visual information inside the test section with regards to the static deflection of the fins, during loading.

The cavities are equipped with many static pressure ports, that can be connected to the available scanner channels, depending on the test requirements. A total of ten additional unsteady pressure probes (Kulite XTE-190), are available for measurements in the cavities, which can be mounted in a wide range of configurations.

Some additional steady pressure ports are in the inlet sections, to allow measurements of the flow in the inlet as well. In addition, six thermocouples provide readings of the inlet and outlet temperatures of the air.

The seal vibration is measured simultaneously, with up to eight strain gauges, whilst any shaft vibration is being monitored with two accelerometers which are mounted on the shaft. An additional six accelerometers are placed externally on the rig cylinders, to investigate if any vibration of the seal will read to an overall rig response. Due to the self-balancing of ND2 modes and above, vibration is only expected for the seal/shaft coupling modes ND0 and ND1.

The air flowrate is measured via a Bronkhorst mass flow meter, which is located upstream of the test facility in the supply pipeline.

All instrumentation is connected to two National Instrument C-RIOs (NI-9045), that are equipped with a wide range of cards, allowing the acquisition of different types of data. One system is thereby dedicated to high-speed data acquisition via the FPGA layer (36 channels at 50kHz simultaneous sampling), whilst the other unit runs in scan-engine-mode and mainly deals with low-speed data capture and valve control.

2.4 Rig operation

Figure-11 shows a detailed overview of the rig's flow control system. Air is supplied from three Ingersoll rotatory-screw compressors, capable of providing up to 1.2kg/s of air at a pressure of 7Bar. The primary pressure regulator at the inlet of the rig, allows to regulate the pressure between 3 and 6 bar, which represents the inlet pressure range. Furthermore, it can maintain these pressures at a flowrate of up to 0.5kg/s of air. A shut-off valve is used to isolate the rig from the main air system when the rig is not being used and in case of an emergency. A series of manual ball valves can be used to set the flow direction of the rig. Figure-10 shows a setup with a flow direction from section 1 to section 2, where V_{1in} and V_{2out} are open, whilst V_{1out} and V_{2in} are closed. Once the flow direction is set, the actuator-valves (Act 1, Act V and Act 2) and pressure control valve can be used to control the operation of the rig.

FIGURE-11: FLOW CONTROL SYSTEM.

Initially, both sides of the rig can be filled to the required upstream pressure value. This is achieved via the venting pipework (Act V), to ensure no significant flow goes across the seal during the filling of the rig. Once both sides are filled to the required starting pressure, the venting valve will be closed, and the pressure control valve will be slowly opened to induce a pressure drop across the seal. The opening of the pressure control valve will continue until a flutter event can be detected, or until the rig reaches its limit with regards to available mass flow. If flutter is present, and the seal vibration levels reach critical limits (HCF or striking the test section), the test rig can be isolated from the supply air via the Act 1 and 2, and the two sides of the rig equalized via the venting actuator (Act V). These three actuators

were chosen to have a quick response time, to ensure the fastest possible pressure changes between the cavities.

2.5 Rig manufacture and Assembly

Two types of steel were chosen for the manufacture of the rig. The shaft and seal were manufactured from steel 17-4-PH-1150, due to its high yield-strength of 720MPa. The cylinders were manufactured from steel S355J2-G3 with a yield-strength of 330MPa. After the manufacture was completed, all the cylinders were tested for cracks and imperfections, with non-destructive ultrasonic methods to ensure they complied with the pressure vessel requirements.

FIGURE-12: PARTIALLY ASSEMBLED TEST RIG.

The rig was assembled inside a sound booth, to ensure that whilst it is running, the operator would not be exposed to excessive noise. Figure-12 shows the partially assembled rig. The rig is mounted on an aluminium skeleton frame, via a series of flanges that form part of the bottom half-cylinders and the test section. The close-up in Figure-12 shows the three layers of honeycomb in the inlet sections, and the fully assembled duct cylinder which ensures the uniformity of flow supplied to the cavities. Figure-13 shows the fully assembled and instrumented test facility, including the supply pipework, the instrumentation and control boxes. Due to the limited space available inside the sound booth, the air supply and control system had to be designed and manufactured with great care, to ensure the assembly and functionality of the seal flutter rig.

FIGURE-13: FULLY ASSEMBLED AND INSTRUMENTED TEST FACILITY.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A series of tests were conducted prior to and during the assembly of the test facility, to ensure its functionality.

3.1 Damping evaluation

One of many concerns when attempting to induce flutter in any test facility, is knowing the amount of structural damping present in the system, due to various connections and interfaces in the assembly, since it will counteract and potentially overshadow the negative damping introduced by the flow. Of particular interest, for the presented test facility, was the structural damping from the interface of the seal and shaft, which arises from the keyless coupling (9). The keyless coupling was used for an easy assembly and disassembly of the seal specimen. To evaluate the damping effect, a series of hammer tests were conducted. Initially the seal was tested under free-free conditions, to evaluate its background material damping, then the seal was mounted to the centre of the shaft via the keyless coupling and the impact tests were repeated. Several locations were impacted, and the response measured via a contactless LDV (Laser Doppler Vibrometer), to ensure accurate identification of resonance frequencies, mode shapes and damping. The first five natural frequencies and damping of the seal, and the seal-shaft assembly, can be seen in Table-2. As expected, the seal alone shows very low levels of damping, with the maximum damping ratio reaching 0.05%. Interestingly, the seal shaft assembly has damping ratios similar to the unassembled case (seal only), showing that the keyless coupling does not add significant damping, at least at the low excitation levels of an impact hammer test.

TABLE-2: MEASURED STRUCTURAL DAMPING – FREE-FREE CONDITIONS.

Mode	SEAL		ASSEMBLY	
	Frequency (Hz)	Damping ratio ζ (%)	Frequency (Hz)	Damping ratio ζ (%)
1	399.5	0.016	154	0.025
2	507.2	0.012	154	0.051
3	738.6	0.018	259	0.019
4	1080	0.014	367	0.043
5	1990	0.048	403	0.013

For a much more realistic case, the shaft was mounted to the rig assembly, where it is supported by two V-edge clamps on either side, and it was loaded axially via two M36 bolts. A new series of hammer tests was then conducted, to identify the damping due to the support system. The resulting damping values in Table-3 show that some modes are now heavily damped, whilst others show a similar damping to the simple assembly case. The first mode, which has one nodal diameter (ND1) mode, is strongly coupled with the shaft, and hence it shows a significant amount of damping due to the friction in the knife edge joints. Fortunately, the higher nodal diameter modes, which are expected to be much more unstable, do not interact with the shaft and hence show extremely low damping values, providing proof

and confidence that the structural damping will not prevent the initiation of seal flutter.

TABLE-3: MEASURED STRUCTURAL DAMPING – SEAL ASSEMBLY MOUNTED IN TEST RIG.

ASSEMBLY MOUNTED ON RIG		
Mode	Frequency (Hz)	Damping ratio ζ (%)
1F-1ND	242	0.42
1F-2ND	404	0.016
1F-3ND	1082	0.011
1F-4ND	2000	0.061

3.2 Initial rig commissioning

A series of initial rig commissioning tests have been completed to demonstrate the capability of the design and to achieve the required flowrates and pressures.

The first test consisted of pressurising the rig gradually, up to its maximum pressure, to identify any structural issues or leaks. No structural problems were observed, but a significant amount of leakage in the rig itself, but also in the supply pipework led to a major rebuild of the rig, to minimise the leakage flow. Figure-14 shows a set of leakage flow tests, conducted with different operating pressures and test numbers, indicating the gradual reduction in leakage flow in the rig over time. Initially, nearly 40 g/s of leakage flow was present in the rig, at a pressure of 6bar, which is close to the expected flow for some seal configurations. After several modifications (leakage flow test 6) the flow was severely reduced, until it fell below the sensitivity of the sensor (1g/s).

FIGURE 14: TESTS OF LEAKAGE FLOW IMPROVEMENTS IN THE RIG.

Further tests were conducted to establish the maximum flow that can be achieved across the rig, and it was demonstrated that the targeted 500g/s could be reached and maintained for a certain amount of time.

At the time of writing of this paper, the commissioning is ongoing, with a series of tests planned to demonstrate the functionality of all the sensors, an evaluation of the flow field uniformity for different flow conditions across the rig, an

optimisation of the actuator activation to minimize the response time of the rig and optimize the controllability of flow and pressure ratios, and finally an initial flutter initiation of a four-fin labyrinth seal.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the development of a novel labyrinth seal flutter test facility (ARIAS), from the conceptual design stages to the initial commissioning tests. The presented rig design allows for the investigation of a wide range of seals under many test conditions, making the rig a very versatile facility to provide better physical understanding of seal flutter phenomena and high-fidelity validation data.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.Phibel.,2009, “Numerical Investigation of Labyrinth Seal Aeroelastic Stability”, *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2009- Power for Land, Sea and Air, GT-2009-60017*.
- [2] T, Miura., N, Sakia., T, Imai., Y, Sakai., 2021, “A Study of Flutter Suppression of Rotating Labyrinth Seal Utilising Stator Fin”, Kawasaki Heavy Industries. *Journal of the Japanese Society of Gas-Turbines, Vol. 49 No.3 -2021.05*.
- [3] Alford, J., 1964. “Protection of Labyrinth Seals from Flexural Vibration”. *Journal of Engineering for Power*, 86, pp. 141–147. also ASME Paper 63-AHGT-9.
- [4] Abbott, D., 1980. “Advances in Labyrinth Seal Aeroelastic Instability Prediction and Prevention”. ASME Paper 80-GT151.
- [5] Ehrich, F., 1968. “Aeroelastic Instability in Labyrinth Seals”. ASME Paper 68-GT-32.
- [6] Lewis, D., Platt, C., and Smith, E., 1979. “Aeroelastic Instability in F100 Labyrinth Air Seals”. *Journal of Aircraft*, 16(7), pp. 484–490. also AIAA Paper 78–1087.
- [7] R., Corall, M., Greco, A., Vega, “Higher Order Conceptual Model for Labyrinth Seal Flutter”, *ASME Journal of Turbomachinery*, v 143, n 7, July 2021.
- [8] R, Corral., M, Greco. And A, Vega., 2022, “Effective Clearance and Differential Gapping Impact on Seal Flutter Modelling and Validation”, *ASME Journal of Turbomachinery. J. Turbomach. Jul 2022, 144(7): 071010 (13 pages)*.
- [9] R. M. Hall., 1997, “Modelling of Rotor/Stator Interaction Dynamics (ROSTADYN)”, *Imperial College London*.
- [10] T., Miura and N. Sakai, “Numerical and Experimental Studies of Labyrinth Seal Aeroelastic Instability”, *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2019, Phoenix, Arizona, 2019*.